

Evaluating the Efficacy of Antibiotic Impregnated Beads for Osteomyelitis in Individuals with DiabetesMehul Shah¹, Girish Parmar², Ashok M Ram³¹Associate Professor, Department of Orthopedics, Shantabaa Medical College & General Hospital Amreli, Gujarat, India²Assistant Professor, Department of Surgery, Shri M P Shah Government Medical College, Jamnagar, Gujarat, India³Private Practitioner, Spandan Hospital and Critical Care Center, Jamnagar, Gujarat, India

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Abstract:

Background and Aim: Diabetic foot infections rank high among the most prevalent skeletal and soft tissue infections in individuals with diabetes. Oral antibiotics with high oral bioavailability and localised delivery of antibiotics in bead form are currently being utilised. This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of antibiotic-impregnated beads in the treatment of osteomyelitis in patients with diabetic feet in an Indian setting. The study also examined the microbiological profile of the wounds.

Material and Methods: In our current main study, the total sample size was 100. The participants were assigned at random to the two groups. In the 'bead' group, antibiotic beads were utilised, while the 'no bead' group received oral antibiotics. Both groups received intravenous antibiotics as a precautionary measure. All patients were evaluated for a period of six months, and ulcers that did not heal within this timeframe were considered as unsuccessful treatment.

Results: The mean age, body mass index, random blood sugar, and HbA1c values did not show any significant differences between the two groups. Our study examined the healing of ulcers in two groups. Out of the 100 patients in both groups, 87 patients experienced healing, while 13 did not. Out of the nine that did not heal, nine were from the group without beads and four were from the group with beads. Among the 87 individuals who experienced healing, 41 were from the group without beads, while the remaining 46 were from the group with beads. The healing association had no significant statistical impact. Staphylococcus aureus was the most commonly found organism.

Conclusion: Individuals in the 'no bead' group faced challenges in accessing hospitals on a daily basis, and some even had to skip their daily dressings due to personal inconveniences. When antibiotic beads are delivered locally, they can increase the concentration of the antibiotic in the surrounding tissue while keeping serum levels low. This helps to minimise any systemic side effects that may occur.

Keywords: Diabetic foot, HbA1c, Osteomyelitis, Staphylococcus aureus.

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Introduction

It is concerning to see the global prevalence of diabetes on the rise, with more than 450 million people affected by this condition. [1] Regrettably, around 20% of individuals with diabetes will need to be hospitalised due to a foot infection caused by their condition. [2] These infections can have severe consequences, causing significant health issues and financial burdens. The pathogenesis can vary, from the immune system attacking the β -cells of the pancreas to the body becoming resistant to insulin. Diabetes mellitus can lead to a range of microvascular complications, such as retinopathy, nephropathy, and neuropathy, which can ultimately result in diabetic foot diseases. Myocardial infarction, transient ischaemia, and stroke are

serious complications that can occur in the blood vessels. Foot ulceration and infections can lead to serious health complications for patients. Diabetic foot patients face a significant lifetime risk of 25%, making it a major contributor to lower limb amputation rates and extended hospital stays. Based on epidemiological studies, it has been found that a significant portion of the population, around 2.5%, is diagnosed with diabetes annually. Additionally, approximately 15% of individuals develop diabetic foot diseases. [3-5] Diabetic foot infections usually begin with ulcers that need a comprehensive treatment approach to prevent them from developing into osteomyelitis. When diabetic foot osteomyelitis (DFO) occurs, it becomes crucial to implement

aggressive treatments in order to prevent the need for amputations. However, in some cases, amputations may be necessary to effectively treat the infection while still maintaining the functionality of the foot. [6,7] Unfortunately, amputations are often linked to challenges in wound healing, increased risk of ulcerations, and the potential need for additional amputations. [8] Therefore, there is a pressing need for new treatments that can help with sterilisation, promote wound healing, and prevent infections from coming back.

When dealing with a foot ulcer in a diabetic patient that exposes the underlying bone, it is important to consider the potential presence of osteomyelitis. To confirm this, an x-ray and bone culture should be conducted to rule out any complications. In the case of osteomyelitis in the diabetic foot, it is possible for an inflamed digit to be present, which may necessitate debridement and culture from the bone. Managing diabetic foot involves three key steps: glycaemic control, proper foot care, and wearing suitable footwear. Managing diabetic foot osteomyelitis continues to be a complex task. In the past, intravenous antibiotics were commonly used for treatment, along with debridement. Using higher concentrations of antibiotics can lead to complications such as nephrotoxicity and ototoxicity. Nevertheless, a significant number of patients are unable to tolerate extended periods of intravenous antibiotic treatment or may experience multi-organ failure as a result of prolonged antibiotic use. Studies have found that there is no significant difference in the effectiveness of oral and intravenous antibiotics for treating diabetic foot osteomyelitis. [9]

Local delivery of antibiotics in the form of beads provides a precise concentration of selected antibiotics directly at the infection site. This is a major breakthrough in the treatment of osteomyelitis in diabetic patients, providing them with a much more convenient option. [10] The beads are carefully prepared in a sterile environment within the operating room before being delicately placed onto the ulcer.

There is very little information available about this topic in the Indian population. This study aimed to evaluate the efficacy of antibiotic-impregnated beads in the treatment of osteomyelitis in patients with diabetic feet in an Indian setting. The study also examined the microbiological profile of the wounds.

Material and Methods

A study was conducted in the general surgery and orthopaedic departments at a Tertiary Care Teaching Institute in India for a duration of 1 year. The data was collected after receiving ethical clearance from the Institutional Research Board and Ethics Committee. Consent was obtained from the patient

and carer for their participation in the study and the use of their data.

According to our pilot study, we found that a sample size of 50 per group would be sufficient. This conclusion was based on a 95% confidence interval and a statistical power of 80% in a 2-sided test. Therefore, our main study consisted of a total sample size of 100. The participants were assigned at random to the two groups.

The patients who visited the outpatient departments of general surgery and podiatry underwent a comprehensive assessment, which included a detailed history and a thorough clinical examination. In the study, all chronic diabetic foot ulcers measuring 5 cm² or smaller were included. Once the patients achieved satisfactory glycaemic control, they underwent debridement in the operation theatre while receiving systemic antibiotics. Additionally, bone cultures were collected for further analysis. The administration of antibiotics specific to the culture was delayed.

In the 'bead' group, antibiotic beads were utilised, while the 'no bead' group received oral antibiotics. Both groups received intravenous antibiotics as a precautionary measure. The most frequently utilised antibiotics were amoxicillin-clavulanic acid and cefoperazone-sulbactam. Both groups of patients were hospitalised for approximately one week before being discharged. Patients were evaluated according to the number of days it took for their wounds to heal. The wound was deemed fully healed once the ulcer had completely epithelialised.

After debriding the wound, the antibiotic beads were prepared according to the culture and sensitivity report and placed over the ulcer with underlying osteomyelitis. The beads were created by combining the necessary antibiotic concentration with a synthetic implant-grade calcium sulphate dihydrate, which promotes quick healing and is both biodegradable and biocompatible. Once the ingredients were thoroughly combined, a seamless paste was created and evenly spread onto the bead mat using the paste applicator. It was left undisturbed to set. The bead mat was flexed to release the beads. The ulcers were treated by placing the dressings on them and covering them with sterile gauzes. The patient or their carer would then replace the dressings every 3 days.

Patients were regularly seen in our outpatient department every three weeks, where their wounds were carefully evaluated. If there is slough or residual infection of the tissue, the medical team will perform debridement and reload antibiotic beads until the wound heals. Patients in the 'no bead' group were discharged with oral antibiotics prescribed according to the culture and sensitivity reports. Patients in this group needed to have their dressings done every day either at the outpatient department or

at local hospitals. It was necessary to review and reassess the wound every three weeks. Patients were evaluated for a duration of six months, and ulcers that did not heal within this timeframe were considered as unsuccessful treatment.

Examining the data through statistical analysis:

The data was compiled and entered into a spreadsheet program (Microsoft Excel 2019) and then exported to the data editor page of SPSS version 19 (SPSS Inc., Chicago, Illinois, USA).

The quantitative variables were described using either means and standard deviations or median and interquartile range, depending on their distribution. The qualitative variables were displayed as counts and percentages. Confidence level and level of significance were set at 95% and 5% respectively for all tests.

Here are the results: Our study included a total of 100 patients, with 50 individuals in each group. The age range of the participants was between 35 and 85 years, with an average age of 58 years in the 'bead' group and 60 years in the 'no bead' group.

Out of the total number of patients, 18 were females and 82 were males, indicating a higher incidence of diabetic foot osteomyelitis in males. The mean age, body mass index, random blood sugar, and HbA1c values showed no statistically significant difference

between the two groups, as indicated in Table 1. Our study examined the healing of ulcers in two groups. Out of the 100 patients in both groups, 87 patients experienced healing, while 13 did not. Out of the nine that did not heal, nine were from the group without beads and four were from the group with beads. Among the 87 individuals who experienced healing, 41 were from the group without beads, while the remaining 46 were from the group with beads. The healing association was not statistically significant, as indicated by a p value of 0.9. In the group without beads, the average healing time was 75.14±30.10, while in the group with beads it was 80.98±28.14. The p value of 0.22 indicated that there was no statistically significant difference between the two groups (Table 1). In the group without beads, 41 participants took 20 days to heal within the first 60 days, 17 participants took 60-120 days, and 4 participants took 120-180 days. In the group with beads, 46 participants took 10 days to heal within the first 60 days, 33 participants took 60-120 days, and 3 participants took 120-180 days. The microbiological profile in both the study groups consisted of 38 *Staphylococcus aureus*, 25 *Enterococcus*, 23 *Klebsiella*, 16 *Pseudomonas*, and 13 *E. coli*. *Staphylococcus aureus* was the most common organism found in both groups of our study. *Enterococcus*, *Klebsiella*, and *Pseudomonas* were subsequently observed. 48 out of 100 patients in both groups exhibited polymicrobial status.

Table 1: Demographics, laboratory and wound characteristics of the study population

Variables	No bead group (n=50)	Bead group (n=50)	P value
Mean age (years)	60.12±5.48	58.98±6.12	0.09
Gender			
Male	42	40	0.12
Female	8	10	
BMI (kg/m ²)	38.50±4.10	39.98±3.14	0.47
Random blood sugar (mg/dl)	190.54±15.47	194.79±12.15	0.68
HbA1c	8.97±0.45	7.80±1.30	0.25
Wound size at presentation (cm ²)	3.50±1.23	4.15±0.36	0.09
Duration of wound at presentation (days)	21.50±4.68	24.50±1.99	0.2
Wound healing			
Yes	41	46	0.09
No	9	4	
Mean duration of wound healing (days)	75.14±30.10	80.98±28.14	0.22

Statistically significance at $p \leq 0.05$

Discussion

Diabetic foot ulcers (DFUs) can be a serious and expensive complication for individuals with diabetes. Even with the right surgical intervention and medical care, 40% of patients experience a recurrence of osteomyelitis, leading to additional surgeries and proximal amputations. [11] In our study, we examined 100 patients who were divided into two groups. Each group consisted of 50 individuals, with ages ranging from 35 to 85 years. The mean age of group 1 was 58, while group 2 had a mean age of 60. Out of the total patients, 18 were

females and 82 were males, indicating a higher prevalence of diabetic foot osteomyelitis among males.

A study conducted at the multi-disciplinary foot clinic at Royal Darwin Hospital in Northern Territory, Australia, from 2003 to 2017, included a total of 513 patients who were diagnosed with diabetic foot ulcers. The average age of the participants was 59.9±12.3 years, with a majority of 62.8% being males. [12] Our research findings also revealed a higher occurrence of diabetic foot osteomyelitis in males. Our study compared the

healing time between two groups. Out of the 100 patients in both groups, 87 patients experienced healing while 13 did not. Out of the nine that did not heal, nine were from the group without beads, while four were from the group with beads. Among the 87 individuals who experienced healing, 41 were from the group without beads, while the remaining 46 were from the group with beads.

Although the healing rate among groups was not statistically significant, it is worth noting that the 'bead' group had an impressive healing rate of 92%. By contrast, the healing rate in the group without beads was only 82%. There was a significantly higher number of patients who did not respond to the 'no bead' therapy compared to the 'bead' group. The average healing time in the group without beads was 75.14 ± 30.10 , while in the group with beads it was 80.98 ± 28.14 . The p value of 0.22 indicates that there is no statistically significant difference between the two groups.

A randomised controlled trial conducted at a single specialist centre demonstrated that patients with forefoot osteomyelitis achieved similar healing rates (75%) regardless of whether they received medical treatment or a primarily surgical approach. Exclusion criteria for the study included patients with peripheral arterial disease, exposed bone, and poorly controlled diabetes. [13] These features are typically found in diabetes foot clinics in real-world settings. There is emerging evidence suggesting that conservative, non-surgical treatment may effectively manage diabetic foot ulcers with osteomyelitis.

A study was conducted at the department of diabetes, University hospitals of Leicester, NHS Trust, UK, where 20 patients with diabetes and nonhealing foot ulcers, along with forefoot osteomyelitis, underwent treatment. The patients were treated with debridement and antibiotic beads containing vancomycin and gentamycin, using HPS calcium sulphate. The subjects were monitored for a duration of 18 months. The presence of osteomyelitis was confirmed in these patients through bone culture and x-ray examination of the foot.

A mixture was created by combining calcium sulphate with 1gm of vancomycin and 80mg of gentamycin. All patients experienced complete healing within a median time of 5 weeks and did not experience any recurrence for a period of 12 months. All patients in the study did not experience any negative reactions. [14] According to a study conducted in Toronto by surgeons from Rambam medical centre in Israel, a group of 15 patients were found to have diabetic foot osteomyelitis. All these patients received local antibiotic therapy as part of their treatment. In an 11-month follow-up study, it was found that out of 15 patients, one had to undergo

amputation while the others were able to heal with the help of local antibiotic treatment. [15] The study lacked a comparison group.

The hospital stay was compared between two groups: one with beads and one without beads. The group that received the 'bead' treatment had a longer hospital stay, as they needed a week of empirical antibiotic treatment and debridement, along with the application of local antibiotic beads based on culture results in the operation theatre. The patients were closely monitored for a duration of two days before being released.

This procedure was performed on an outpatient basis in just a few hours. The other group was treated in a similar manner, with the exception that they were sent home with oral antibiotics and instructed to change their dressings daily. Most of our study findings aligned with the research conducted in other centres, as previously mentioned.

Antibiotic bead treatment is a viable option for patients who are unable to take antibiotics orally or intravenously due to their systemic condition. It has been observed that antibiotic beads have a positive impact on reducing hospital visits and the need for daily dressings. The surgeon found it easy to apply and the patients tolerated it well. Our study found that the antibiotic 'bead' group had a longer healing duration, but a higher number of patients in this group had fully healed wounds.

The study did not compare the economic aspects of both treatments, which is an important limitation to consider.

Conclusion

Using antibiotic beads can enhance patient convenience by minimising hospital visits and the requirement for daily dressing, all while maintaining a high healing rate.

Some individuals in the group without access to hospitals faced challenges in receiving daily care, and a few even had to forgo their regular dressings due to personal inconveniences. When antibiotic beads are delivered locally, they help increase the concentration of the antibiotic in the surrounding tissue while keeping serum levels low.

This approach effectively minimises systemic side effects. Health professionals are now opting for oral antibiotics and antibiotic beads to treat osteomyelitis, as they offer better bioavailability and higher tissue concentration without causing systemic toxicity. This approach is replacing the previous method of using intravenous antibiotics. Patients' quality of life has been greatly enhanced and hospital stays have been shortened as a result of this improvement.

References

1. Ingelfinger JR, Jarcho JA: Increase in the incidence of diabetes and its implications. *N Engl J Med.* 2017; 376:1473-4. 10.1056/NEJMe1616575
2. Bandyk DF: The diabetic foot: pathophysiology, evaluation, and treatment. *Semin Vasc Surg.* 2018; 31:43-8. 10.1053/j.semvascsurg.2019.02.001
3. Barwell ND, Devers MC, Kennon B, Hopkinson HE, McDougall C, Young MJ, et al. Diabetic foot infection: antibiotic therapy and good practice recommendations. *Int J Clin Pract.* 2017; 71(10).
4. Papanas N, Maltezos E. The diabetic foot: established and emerging treatments. *Acta Clin Belg.* 2007; 62(4):230-8.
5. Kumhar M, Dara N, Saini T. Foot wear and footcare knowledge- an independent risk factor for diabetic foot in Indian diabetics. *Indian Med Gaz.* 2014; 4.
6. Pitocco D, Spanu T, Di Leo M, et al.: Diabetic foot infections: a comprehensive overview. *Eur Rev Med Pharmacol Sci.* 2019; 23:26-37. 10.26355/eurrev_201904_17471
7. Mills JL, Conte MS, Armstrong DG, et al.: The Society for Vascular Surgery lower extremity threatened limb classification system: risk stratification based on wound, ischemia, and foot infection (WIFI). *J Vasc Surg.* 2014; 59:220-34. 10.1016/j.jvs.2013.08.00
8. Shaikh N, Vaughan P, Varty K, Coll AP, Robinson AH: Outcome of limited forefoot amputation with primary closure in patients with diabetes. *Bone Joint J.* 2013; 95-B: 1083-7. 10.1302/0301-620X.95B8.31280
9. Senneville E, Robineau O. Treatment options for diabetic foot osteomyelitis. *Expert Opin Pharmacother.* 2017; 18(8):759-65.
10. Panagopoulos P, Drosos G, Maltezos E, Papanas N. Local antibiotic delivery systems in diabetic foot osteomyelitis: time for one step beyond? *Int J Low Extrem Wounds.* 2015; 14(1):87-91.
11. Gauland C: Managing lower-extremity osteomyelitis locally with surgical debridement and synthetic calcium sulfate antibiotic tablets. *Adv Skin Wound Care.* 2011; 24:515-23.
12. Jeyaraman K, Berhane T, Hamilton M, Chandra AP, Falhammar H. Mortality in patients with diabetic foot ulcer: a retrospective study of 513 cases from a single Centre in the Northern Territory of Australia. *BMC Endocr Disord.* 2019; 19.
13. Lazaro-Martinez JL, Aragon-Sanchez J, Garcia-Morales E. Antibiotics versus conservative surgery for treating diabetic foot osteomyelitis: a randomized comparative trial. *Diabetes Care.* 2014; 37:789-795.
14. Jogia RM, Modha DE, Nisal K, Berrington R, Kong MF. Use of highly purified synthetic calcium sulfate impregnated with antibiotics for the management of diabetic foot ulcers complicated by osteomyelitis. *Diabetes Care.* 2015; 38(5):e79-80.
15. Melamed EA, Peled E. Antibiotic impregnated cement spacer for salvage of diabetic osteomyelitis. *Foot Ankle Int.* 2012; 33(3):213-9.